

A STUDY OF ANXIETY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG UNDER GRADUATE (UG) STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study is conducted to find out the level of academic anxiety, academic achievement and relationship between academic anxiety and academic achievement among under graduate students. The anxiety scale developed by Dr. D.N. Srivastava and Dr. Govind Tiwari for Academic anxiety and for Academic achievement of under graduate students their 12th standard percentage was used for the present study and descriptive survey research method employed in the present study. A sample of under graduate students selected by using random sampling technique. The total sample consisted of 120 (60 Science and 60 Arts) under graduate students and the age range were 17 to 21 years. The obtained data was analyzed by using mean, standard deviation, and t-test. The analyzed results revealed that 1. There is average level of anxiety and academic achievement found among UG students. 2. There is no significant difference found in anxiety and academic achievement in the context of stream, sex and locality of UG students. 3. There is very weak negative relationship found between anxiety and academic achievement among UG students

KEYWORDS: Academic Anxiety, Academic Achievement and Under Graduate Students.

INTRODUCTION

Education in the broadest way is any act or experience which has an influential impact on the mind, character or physical ability of a person and in its technical sense education is the procedure by which society purposefully transmits its accumulated knowledge, values and skills from one generation to another through instructions. Education is similar to housing and food. It is regarded as essential to existence, much as food and shelter are for the body and the intellect, respectively, and education is for health. It is also considered to be knowledge acquisition in its more restrictive definition (Kumar et al. 2014).

Education includes developing beliefs, skills, and talents in addition to absorbing material from textbooks. This is a procedure that goes on throughout life and is promoted by almost every experience in life (McDonald, 2001). It assists people in making career plans that will be helpful in creating a new society with progressive principles. Thus, education result in changing both individual lives as well as that of the entire community.

Anxiety is an essential part of being human which have existed throughout the entire existence of mankind. It is a necessary aspect of being human. Anxiety, disorders and panic attacks have been described by numerous notable and prominent historical figures. Everybody experiences it at some point in their lives, whether it is from interpersonal conflicts, financial worries, family responsibilities, or overload at work, school, or home. Anxiety has a dual impact on a student's life, contributing significantly to his academic achievement.

In the words of Stephen Paul (1982)- “without anxiety, we would probably all be asleep at our desks.” The British poet W.H. Auden called the twentieth century “The age of anxiety.”

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The goal of education is the holistic development of the learner's personality over the course of a lifetime. A person can receive their education in a number of ways, including through their family, community, school, college, and institutions. The institutional environment of schools, colleges, and universities facilitates successful learning and the development of lifelong competences and abilities across a wide range of subject areas. For instance, social studies, science, math, communication, and language. Academic achievement is defined as the knowledge, skills, and abilities attained inside the institutional framework of schools, colleges, and universities.

There are benefits and drawbacks to everything in the cosmos. There are advantages and disadvantages to anxiety as well. It is true that having a lot of worry makes it difficult to focus and remember things, which are essential for doing well in school. However, most of us wouldn't be motivated to write papers, study for tests, or complete everyday tasks if we didn't experience anxiety. A healthy dose of worry really improves academic achievement by igniting motivation.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Today, anxiety is a common phenomenon of everybody's life. It plays a crucial role in human existence because all of us are the victim of anxiety in different ways. Students' performance is impacted by anxiety not only in the classroom but also in other areas of their lives. Anxiety has been shown to have a major impact on students' academic performance and learning. Anxiety is hampering students' academic performance. It is closely related to academic success and is influenced by a number of factors, including switching schools or colleges, the environment of such institutions, the teachers there, the difficulty of particular topics like maths and English, the pressure of work, tests and exams, etc.

Therefore, it is imperative to look into graduate students' anxiousness. Teachers and students may benefit from knowing more about the influence of anxiety on academic achievement from this inquiry. It may also assist teachers better advise and motivate their students based on their needs and backgrounds.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Das and Mallik (2021) conducted a study on purposively selected sample of 160 students from four secondary schools of Balasore district, Odisha. The researchers intended to examine and enhance the "learning achievement of tribal secondary school level learner in relation to their test anxiety". They adopted the anxiety scale developed by Michael Frizell for the data collection and t-test for analysis of data. The result of the study showed that test anxiety and learning achievement are intimately correlated and extents of anxiety affect the scholastic achievement of the learners.

Muthaiyan and Lingeswaran (2021) founded that private management school students have high anxiety in test when compared to government school students. This study was best on normative random sampling and sample size was 300 students chosen from Chetpet Talluk in Thiruvannamalai District, Tamilnadu, India. The data was collected by using test anxiety scale adopted from Prof. V.P. Sharma and analyzed by using SPSS. The hypothesis of this study was tested by using t-test and f-test and was titled under the heading "test anxiety among IXth standard students with respect to some variables."

Jahan (2020) conducted a study on adjustment, anxiety and academic achievement of school students of South Assam. It seeks to analyze the relationship between adjustment (total and in different areas i.e., home, social, emotional, educational), anxiety and academic achievement of school students. This study was based on survey type research method with sample size of

120 students from four Kendriya Vidyalayas of Cachar District of Assam. The results of the study showed that a greater number of high achievers had high anxiety than the low achievers.

Halder U.K. (2018) studied the relation between “English language anxiety and academic achievement” and found that there is a negative correlation between English language anxiety and academic achievement of rural and urban students. The study revealed that the students’ anxiety for English language is one of the major issues for their academic achievement. Therefore, students’ parents and the teachers should be more conscious about the issue of second language anxiety and measures to be taken to make it more interesting in the classroom.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To find out the level of anxiety and academic achievement among UG students.
2. To find out the significant difference if any the anxiety and academic achievement of UG students with respect to their stream, sex and locality.
3. To find out the relationship between anxiety and academic achievement among UG students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses were formulated

1. There is average level of anxiety and academic achievement exists among UG students.
2. There is no significant difference in anxiety between science and arts UG students.
3. There is no significant difference in anxiety between male and female UG students.
4. There is no significant difference in anxiety between UG students belong to Urban and Rural areas.
5. There is no significant difference in academic anxiety between science and arts UG students.
6. There is no significant difference in academic anxiety between male and female UG students.
7. There is no significant difference in academic anxiety between UG students belong to Urban and Rural areas.
8. There is no significant relationship between anxiety and academic achievement among under graduate students.

DELIMITATION

The present study is delimited to the age group of 17-21 years, science and arts under graduate students of Urban and rural areas of Bareilly region.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the objectives of the study the Descriptive Survey Method is applied by the researcher.

SAMPLE & SAMPLING

All the students of under graduate level colleges of Bareilly district were the population of this study. In the present research, the researchers selected their sample of 120 under graduate students from Bareilly district.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION

After getting permission by the Principals/ HoDs/ Class Teachers of the respective college/ Department/ Class, the UG students were contacted. The aim of the study was explained to them. It was recommended of the students to thoroughly read the directions and to seek clarification as needed. There is no time restriction. Still, it took around thirty-forty minutes to finish. Following the completion of the scale, the scoring was completed in accordance with the manual's instructions.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

The investigator used Mean, Standard Deviation and ‘t’- test for differential statistical analysis of data and for testing the hypotheses.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

H.1. There is average level of anxiety and academic achievement exists among UG students.

Table 1 & 2: Percentage Level of anxiety and academic achievement of UG Students of Bareilly District.

Table No. 1				
Sr. No	Levels of Anxiety	Number of students (120)	Grade	Anxiety level of UG students (In Percentage)
		Score range		
1	Extremely High	47 & above	A	47.5
2	High	40 to 46	B	13.33
4	Average	27 to 39	C	30
6	Low	19 to 26	D	5.83
7	Extremely Low	18 & below	E	3.33

Table No. 2				
Sr. No	Levels of Academic Achievement	Number of students (120)	Grade	Academic Achievement of UG students (In Percentage)
		Score range		
1	Very Good	87 & above	A	1.67
2	Good	74 to 86.99	B	31.67
4	Average	61 to 73.99	C	50.83
6	Low	48 to 60.99	D	13.33
7	Very Low	47.99 & below	E	2.5

Fig. 1 & 2: Percentage Level of anxiety and academic achievement of UG Students.

On the basis of the content of **table no. 1**, it is revealed that 47.5% of students possess average level of anxiety with the grade C, 30% of students possess high level of anxiety with the grade B, and 13.34% of students process extremely high level of anxiety with the grade A. The percentage of students with low level of anxiety with grade D is 5.83% and with extremely low level of anxiety with grade E is 3.33%. The maximum percentage of students possess average level of anxiety.

Furthermore **table no. 2** indicates that 50.83% of student possess average level of academic achievement with the grade C. The percentage of students with good level of academic achievement with grade B is 31.67% and the percentage of students with very good level of academic achievement is 1.67% with grade A. The low level of academic achievement exists in 13.33% students with grade D and very low level of academic achievement exists in 2.5% of students with grade E. The maximum percentage of students possess average level of academic achievement.

Therefore, the first hypothesis on the basis of above findings stated that- "**H.1. There is average level of anxiety and academic achievement exists among UG students.**", failed to reject.

H.2. There is no significant difference in anxiety between science and arts UG students.

Table 3: Differential statistics of anxiety of Science and Arts UG Student.

Table No. 3					
Sr. No.	Group	Number of Student (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)	t-value degree of freedom (df)= 118
1	Science	61	47.049	13.0138	1.06
2	Arts	59	44.17	16.3356	

***Significance at 0.05 Level= 1.98**

Fig. 3: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for anxiety of science and arts UG Student.

The study of contents of **table no. 3** reveals that the mean value of science students is 47.049 and mean value of art student is 44.16 which indicates that the mean value of science students is higher than that of art students. The value of standard deviation for science students is 13.013 and for art students is 16.33. It also represents the slight increment in the value of standard deviation of art students. The calculated t -value is 1.06 which is tested on 0.05 level of significance at degree of freedom 118. The calculated t-value is lower than tabulated value.

Therefore, the hypothesis stated- “There is no significant difference in anxiety between science and arts UG students,” failed to reject.

H.3. There is no significant difference in anxiety between male and female UG students.

Table 4: Differential statistics of anxiety of male and female UG Students.

Table No. 4					
Sr. No.	Group	Number of Student (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)	t-value degree of freedom (df)= 118
1	Male	59	44.864	15.0033	0.56
2	Female	61	46.377	14.584	

***Significance at 0.05 Level= 1.98**

Fig. 4: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for anxiety of male and female UG Student.

As the data presented in **table no. 4** indicates that the mean value of male students is 44.8644 and mean value of female students is 46.377. The mean value of female student is more than the male students. The value of standard deviation for male students is 15.0033 and for female students is 14.584. It represents the slight increment in the value of standard deviation for male students. The calculated t -value is 0.56 which is tested on 0.05 level of significance at degree of freedom 118. The calculated t-value is lower than tabulated value.

Thus, the hypothesis stated- “There is no significant difference in anxiety between male and female UG students,” failed to reject.

H.4. There is no significant difference in anxiety between the UG students belong to Urban and Rural areas.

Table 5: Differential statistics of anxiety of Urban and Rural UG Students.

Table No. 5					
Sr. No.	Group	Number of Student (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)	t-value degree of freedom (df)= 118
1	Urban	61	47.639	14.8953	1.51
2	Rural	59	43.559	14.4331	

***Significance at 0.05 Level= 1.98**

Fig. 5: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for anxiety of Urban and Rural UG Student.

An overview of the content of **table no. 5** shows that mean value of urban students is 47.6393 and that of rural students is 43.5593. The standard deviation value for urban student age 14.8953 and for rural student is 14.4331. There is slight increment in the mean value of urban students and the value of standard deviation is slightly more for urban students. The t-value at 0.05 significance level is 1.51 at degree of freedom 118. The calculated t-value is less than critical value of t-distribution.

Therefore, the hypothesis stated- “There is no significant difference in anxiety between UG students belong to urban and rural areas,” failed to reject.

H.5. There is no significant difference in academic achievement between science and arts UG students.

Table 6: Differential statistics of academic achievement of science and art UG Students.

Table No. 6					
Sr. No.	Group	Number of Student (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)	t-value degree of freedom (df)= 98
1	Science	61	70.403	9.7521	1.37
2	Arts	59	68.028	9.01	

***Significance at 0.05 Level= 1.98**

Fig. 6: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for academic achievement of science and art UG Student.

The study of the contents of **table No. 6** reveals that the mean value of science stream students is 70.4028 and that of art stream students is 68.0276. The mean score of science students is slightly higher than the art stream students. The value of standard deviation for science students is 9.7521 and that of art students is 9.01. The calculated t-value is 1.37 at 0.05 significance level and degree of freedom is 118. The calculated value is lower than tabulated value.

Therefore, the hypothesis stated- "There is no significant difference in academic achievement between science and art students," failed to reject.

H.6. There is no significant difference in academic achievement between male and female UG students.

Table 7: Differential statistics of academic achievement of male and female UG Students.

Table No. 7					
Sr. No.	Group	Number of Student (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)	t-value degree of freedom (df)= 118

1	Male	59	67.703	10.3774	1.75
2	Female	61	70.717	8.2322	

***Significance at 0.05 Level= 1.98**

Fig. 7: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation for academic achievement of male and female UG Student.

At the data presented in **table No. 7** indicates that the mean score of male students is 67.7029 and mean score of female students 70.7169. The value of mean is slightly more in case of female students. The standard deviation score for male student is 10.3774 and the standard deviation score for female students is 8.2322. The t-value is 1.75 calculated at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom is 118. The calculated t-value is slightly lower than the tabulated value of t-test.

Thus, the seventh hypothesis stated- "There is no significance difference in academic achievement between male and female students," failed to reject.

H.7. There is no significant difference in academic achievement between the UG students belong to Urban and Rural areas.

Table 8: Differential statistics of academic achievement of science and art UG Students.

Sr. No.	Group	Number of Student (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)	t-value degree of freedom (df)= 118
1	Urban	61	70.409	9.59	1.38
2	Rural	59	68.021	9.1863	

***Significance at 0.05 Level= 1.98**

Fig. 8: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation academic achievement of Urban and Rural UG Student.

The investigation of contents of **table No. 8** represented that the mean score of students belong to urban areas of Bareilly region is 70.4093 and the mean score of students belong to rural areas of Bareilly region is 68.0208. The mean score of students belong to urban areas is slightly higher than the students belong to rural areas. The value of standard deviation for students belong to urban areas of Bareilly region is 9.59 and the value of standard deviation for students belong to rural areas of Bareilly region is 9.1863. The calculated t-value is 1.38 which is calculated at level of significance 0.05 and degree of freedom is 118. The calculated t-value is lower than the tabulated value.

Therefore, the hypothesis stated- "There is no significant difference in academic achievement between UG students belong to urban and rural areas," failed to reject.

H.8. There is no significant relationship between anxiety and academic achievement among UG students.

Table 9: Correlation co-efficient of anxiety and academic achievement among UG Students.

Table No. 9				
Correlation between the anxiety and academic achievement among UG students				
Sr. No.	Group	Mean score	Number of student (N)	correlation coefficient (r)
1	Anxiety of UG students	45.633	120	-0.13
2	Academic achievement of UG students	69.242		

p>0.05

The investigation of contents of **table no. 9** reveals that the mean score of anxiety of graduate students is 45.63 and the mean score of academic achievement of UG students is 69.24. The correlation coefficient (r) between the above two variables is -0.13 which is calculated by Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r) formula with the sample size 120. The coefficient value -0.13 shows that there is a **feeble negative correlation** i.e., very week relationship between

the variables. When anxiety increases, the academic achievement also decreases feebly or vice versa.

Therefore, the hypothesis stated- “There is no significant relationship between anxiety and academic achievement among UG students,” has been rejected.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

After analysis of the data, the study has yielded interesting and important results which are as follows-

1. At UG level, there is average level of anxiety and academic achievement exists among students. The reason may be that students are facing almost favorable and average family climate, social climate and have same interest, mentality and lifestyle.
2. There is no significant difference in anxiety between science and art UG students the reason may be the similar environment (family and social), similar educational opportunities, similar lifestyle etc.
3. At UG level, there is no significant difference in anxiety between male and female students. The reason may be the same environment i.e., family and social for male and female students, equal educational opportunities, same attitude and aim towards life.
4. There is no significant difference in anxiety between UG students belong to urban and rural areas, because the modern era has provided basic necessities and basic educational opportunities to almost all parts of the world. This reduces the gap between the urban and rural students. They have same environment, educational opportunities or stressful conditions.
5. At UG level, there is no significant difference in academic achievement between science and art students. The reason may be that students have same environment, intelligence, maturity and educational opportunities.
6. There is no significant difference in academic achievement between male and female UG students. The reason may be that in present time the male and female students do not face discrimination in educational field. They may be provided same environment and educational opportunities.
7. At UG level, there is no significant difference in academic achievement between the academic achievements of students belongs to urban and rural areas. The innovations and development of technology has reduced the educational gap between urban and rural areas. The students are able to study at far places and got equal educational opportunities and environment.
8. At UG level, there is very weak negative relationship found between anxiety and academic achievement among UG students. The reason may be that due to advancement and various innovations in educational field students are able to cope up with anxiety. They take anxiety as positive aspect and concentrate more on studies to improve their academic achievement. Most of the time anxiety is negatively related to academic achievement of students.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The ultimate aim of every research investigation is to reach conclusions based on research findings which can somehow improve the educational conditions either short term or long term and sometimes both.

Today, anxiety is a common phenomenon of every day's life. It plays a crucial role in human life because all of us are the victims of anxiety in different ways. In student's life, it is evident that feelings and worry related anxiety are sources of decrement in student achievement. The high level of anxiety interferes with concentration and memory which are critical for academic achievement. Student's academic achievement can be improved by training or educating students about handling stressful situations in academic life. If students can manage their anxiety, it can assist in improved achievement.

The results and findings of this study may provide information to teachers and students about the anxiety and its impact on academic achievement of UG students. It may help teachers to guide and motivate students according to their requirement and background. Academic programs in institution should also focus on grooming students in skill to stabilize their emotional response to potentially difficult situations. There are various measures and strategies which can be applied by faculty members to handle anxiety among students such as task orientation and preparation, positive thinking, seeking social support, avoidance, relaxation training, coaching, guided imagery, self-instructional training etc.

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